

Computation of Analog Theorem for Dirichlet Eta Function and Riemann Zeta Function

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Abstract: This paper discusses how the Dirichlet eta function relates to the alternative harmonic series and the Riemann zeta function in more detail. In this article, theorems on series involving the alternative harmonic series, the Dirichlet eta function, and the Riemann zeta function are provided to improve the research techniques further in the area of analytic number theory.

MSC Classification codes: 11R59, 65D20

Keywords: computation, dirichlet series, geometric series, zeta function

1. Introduction

In the earlier days, geometric series [1-20] with positive exponents served as a vital role in the development of differential and integral calculus [41] and also in the Euler product, the Dirichlet eta function, and the Riemann zeta function. Geometric series have significant applications in physics, engineering, biology, economics, finance, management, queueing theory, computer science and medicine [5]. Also, the product of geometric series [21-40] with prime numbers plays a vital role in the sum of natural numbers and harmonic series [41-49].

2. Dirichlet Eta function relating to Alternative Harmonic Series

The harmonic series is defined by

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n} = 1 + \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{3} + \frac{1}{4} + \frac{1}{5} + \frac{1}{6} + \frac{1}{7} + \frac{1}{8} + \frac{1}{9} + \dots$$

and the alternative harmonic series is shown below:

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{n+1}}{n} = 1 - \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{3} - \frac{1}{4} + \frac{1}{5} - \frac{1}{6} + \frac{1}{7} - \frac{1}{8} + \dots = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{n-1}}{n}.$$

The Dirichlet eta function relating to the alternative harmonic series is defined by

$$\eta(s) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{n-1}}{n^s} = 1 - \frac{1}{2^s} + \frac{1}{3^s} - \frac{1}{4^s} + \frac{1}{5^s} - \frac{1}{6^s} + \frac{1}{7^s} - \frac{1}{8^s} + \dots$$

The Dirichlet eta function $\eta(s)$ converges for any complex number s and $Re(s) > 0$.

Theorem 2.1: The sum of alternative harmonic series is equal to $\ln 2$.

$$i. e. \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{n+1}}{n} = \ln 2 \quad \text{OR} \quad \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{n-1}}{n} = \ln 2.$$

Proof. This theorem is proved using the infinite geometric series as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Let } S &= 1 + x + x^2 + x^3 + x^4 + x^5 + x^6 + x^7 + \dots \\ \Rightarrow xS &= x + x^2 + x^3 + x^4 + x^5 + x^6 + x^7 + x^8 + \dots \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Then, } (S - xS) &= 1 \Rightarrow (1 - x)S = 1 \Rightarrow \frac{1}{1 - x} = S. \\ \text{i.e. } \frac{1}{1 - x} &= 1 + x + x^2 + x^3 + x^4 + x^5 + x^6 + x^7 + \dots \end{aligned}$$

Integrating on both sides with respect to x :

$$\int \frac{1}{1 - x} dx = \int (1 + x + x^2 + x^3 + x^4 + x^5 + x^6 + x^7 + \dots) dx.$$

First, let us find the solution of $\int \frac{1}{1 - x} dx$.

$$\text{Let } u = 1 - x; \quad du = -dx; \quad dx = -du.$$

$$\text{Then, } \int \frac{1}{1 - x} dx = - \int \frac{1}{u} du = - \ln u = - \ln(1 - x).$$

$$\text{Now, } \int (1 + x + x^2 + x^3 + x^4 + x^5 + x^6 + x^7 + \dots) dx = - \ln(1 - x).$$

$$\Rightarrow x + \frac{x^2}{2} + \frac{x^3}{3} + \frac{x^4}{4} + \frac{x^5}{5} + \frac{x^6}{6} + \frac{x^7}{7} + \frac{x^8}{8} + \dots = - \ln(1 - x).$$

$$\Rightarrow \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{x^n}{n} \dots = - \ln(1 - x) \Rightarrow - \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{x^n}{n} = \ln(1 - x).$$

Substituting $x = -1$ on both sides:

$$- \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^n}{n} = \ln(1 - (-1)) \Rightarrow \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{n+1}}{n} = \ln 2 \quad \text{OR} \quad \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{n-1}}{n} = \ln 2.$$

3. Relation between Dirichlet Eta Function and Riemann Zeta Function

The Riemann zeta function for all complex numbers is defined by

$$\zeta(s) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^s} = 1 + \frac{1}{2^s} + \frac{1}{3^s} + \frac{1}{4^s} + \frac{1}{5^s} + \frac{1}{6^s} + \frac{1}{7^s} + \dots, \quad \forall \operatorname{Re}(s) > 1.$$

The Dirichlet eta function is shown below:

$$\eta(s) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{n-1}}{n^s} = 1 - \frac{1}{2^s} + \frac{1}{3^s} - \frac{1}{4^s} + \frac{1}{5^s} - \frac{1}{6^s} + \frac{1}{7^s} - \frac{1}{8^s} + \dots$$

The relation between the Dirichlet eta function and the Riemann zeta function is shown below:

$$\textbf{Theorem 3.1: } \eta(s) = (1 - 2^{1-s})\zeta(s) \quad \text{OR} \quad \zeta(s) = \frac{1}{1 - 2^{1-s}} \eta(s)$$

Proof. Let prove this theorem as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}\zeta(s) - \eta(s) &= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^s} - \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{n-1}}{n^s} = \frac{1}{1^s} - \frac{1}{1^s} + \frac{1}{2^s} + \frac{1}{2^s} + \frac{1}{3^s} - \frac{1}{3^s} + \frac{1}{4^s} + \frac{1}{4^s} + \dots \\ \zeta(s) - \eta(s) &= \frac{2}{2^s} + \frac{2}{4^s} + \frac{2}{6^s} + \frac{2}{8^s} + \frac{2}{10^s} + \frac{2}{12^s} + \dots = 2 \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(2n)^s} = \frac{2}{2^s} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^s} \\ \zeta(s) - \eta(s) &= 2^{1-s} \zeta(s) \Rightarrow \zeta(s) - 2^{1-s} \zeta(s) = \eta(s). \\ \therefore \eta(s) &= (1 - 2^{1-s}) \zeta(s) \text{ OR } \zeta(s) = \frac{1}{1 - 2^{1-s}} \eta(s).\end{aligned}$$

It is understood that the Dirichlet eta function is the alternative Riemann zeta function.

4. Theorem for Dirichlet Eta Function and Riemann Zeta Function

The analog theorem for the Riemann zeta function is stated by

Theorem 4.1: $\sum_{s=2}^{\infty} (\zeta(s) - 1) = 1.$

Proof. Let us prove this theorem using the Riemann zeta function.

$$\sum_{s=2}^{\infty} (\zeta(s) - 1) = \sum_{s=2}^{\infty} \left(\sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^s} \right) = \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \left(\sum_{s=2}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^s} \right) = \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \left(\left\{ \sum_{s=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^s} \right\} - \left\{ 1 + \frac{1}{n} \right\} \right),$$

where $\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^s}$ is an infinite geometric series.

Now,
$$\sum_{s=2}^{\infty} (\zeta(s) - 1) = \sum_{s=2}^{\infty} \left(\left\{ \frac{1}{1 - \frac{1}{n}} \right\} - \left\{ 1 + \frac{1}{n} \right\} \right) = \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n(n-1)}.$$

Here,
$$\frac{1}{n(n-1)} = \frac{1}{n-1} - \frac{1}{n}$$

Thus,
$$\sum_{s=2}^{\infty} (\zeta(s) - 1) = \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n(n-1)} = \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(n-1)} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n}.$$

$$\sum_{s=2}^{\infty} (\zeta(s) - 1) = \left(1 + \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{3} + \frac{1}{4} + \dots \right) - \left(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{3} + \frac{1}{4} + \dots \right).$$

By simplifying this equation, we conclude that

$$\sum_{s=2}^{\infty} (\zeta(s) - 1) = 1.$$

Next, the analog theorem for the Dirichlet eta function is shown below:

Theorem 4.2: $\sum_{s=2}^{\infty} (\eta(s) - 1) = 1 - 2 \ln 2.$

Proof. Let us prove this theorem using the Dirichlet eta function

$$\sum_{s=2}^{\infty} (\eta(s) - 1) = \sum_{s=2}^{\infty} \left(\sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{n-1}}{n^s} \right) = \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} (-1)^{n-1} \left(\sum_{s=2}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^s} \right).$$

We can simplify this equation using the theorem 4.1.

$$\sum_{s=2}^{\infty} (\eta(s) - 1) = \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{n-1}}{n(n-1)} = \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{n-1}}{(n-1)} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{n-1}}{n}.$$

Here,
$$\sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{n-1}}{(n-1)} = \frac{-1}{1} + \frac{1}{2} - \frac{1}{3} + \dots = -\left(1 - \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{3} - \dots\right) = -\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{n-1}}{n}.$$

$$\sum_{s=2}^{\infty} (\eta(s) - 1) = -\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{n-1}}{n} - \left(\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{n-1}}{n} - 1\right).$$

In this article, the theorem 2.1 states that
$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{n-1}}{n} = \ln 2.$$

Thus,
$$\sum_{s=2}^{\infty} (\eta(s) - 1) = -\ln 2 - (\ln 2 - 1) = -\ln 2 - \ln 2 + 1.$$

By simplifying this equation, we conclude that

$$\sum_{s=2}^{\infty} (\eta(s) - 1) = 1 - 2 \ln 2.$$

5. Conclusion

In this article, the author has been proved several theorems on series involving the alternative harmonic series, the Dirichlet eta function, and the Riemann zeta function in detail. This idea can enable the scientific researchers for further involvement in research and development.

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